

“Predefined Collaborative Approaches”

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SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. Its aim is to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until project end, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

The deliverable D1.2 "Predefined Collaborative Approaches" (PCAs) is part of Work Package (WP) 1: "Human-centred development of the INDUSAC co-creation methodology" of the project "Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia collaborations" (INDUSAC). A PCA is a generalised blueprint for a specific type of a challenge. Each PCA represents an according template for companies to guide them in creating individual challenges.

The goal of the task (sub-task 1.1.3) leading to this deliverable is to describe the process of designing and iteratively improving the PCAs that meet the following criteria:

- The PCAs can be completed within a timeframe of four to eight weeks.
- The PCAs cover the INDUSAC cross-cutting areas.
- The PCAs apply to a wide range of sectors targeted.
- The PCAs are easily modifiable.
- The PCAs have a future-oriented task definition.
- The PCAs are a component of the early phases of product development processes.
- The PCAs enable further training of students and researchers.
- The PCAs result in the development of a deliverable for companies.

Based on creativity workshops and several feedback rounds with the WP1-team, nine different standardised templates, the nine PCAs, can now be filled with content adapted to the company's needs. These templates are designed to produce different results using different tools and methods. Each template is labelled with a title and a brief explanation of the area it covers, providing a basis for challenges that can be tailored to the needs of any organisation. As a result, the PCAs can be used by any company in any sector. Using these PCAs, multiple challenges can be created within a single PCA, and all can be published on the INDUSAC platform for use by interested teams.

In this deliverable, the topics of the PCAs are presented, as well as the basic template from which the specific templates for each PCA have been derived.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BAX	BAX Innovation Consulting SL
BIC	Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley
CCIPB	Pecs-Baranyai Kereskedelmi es Iparkamara
CIT UPC	UPC Technology Center
CUT	Cyprus University of Technology
EIT	EIT Manufacturing East GmbH
FM	Final meeting
INDUSAC	Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for INDUSty-ACademia collaborations
INNO	Innoget / INNOVAWIN 2006 SL
JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute
KO	Kick-off meeting
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
MS	Milestone meeting
PCA	Predefined Collaborative Approach
PSS	Product service system
SWOT	Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat
WP	Work Package

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT	3
ABSTRACT	4
LIST OF ACRONYMS	5
I. INTRODUCTION	7
1. Overview of Task.....	7
2. Introduction Predefined Collaborative Approaches.....	7
II. PREDEFINED COLLABORATIVE APPROACHES	9
1. PCA1: Customer Needs (and Product Properties) of Tomorrow.....	9
2. PCA2: Finding White Spots in the Product Portfolio	11
3. PCA3: Marketing Campaign of the Future	12
4. PCA4: Feel the Future Platform – Developing a Digital Platform Based on a Market Analysis.....	13
5. PCA5: Service and Product Ideas of the Future (Basis Persona).....	14
6. PCA6: Service and Product Ideas of the Future (Basis Scenarios).....	49
7. PCA7: Business Plan – Reduce Your Risk and Optimise Your Planning	50
8. PCA8: Innovative Product Ideas That Solve the Customer Pain.....	51
9. PCA9: Business Model: Adding a Service to my Product – Building a PSS (Product Service System)	52
10. PCA Basic Template.....	53
III. CONCLUSION	57
IV. LIST OF FIGURES	58

I. INTRODUCTION

1. Overview of Task

As stated in this project's Grant Agreement: "This sub-task aims to define a manageable number (9-15) of Predefined Collaborative Approaches. KIT will lead this sub-task in collaboration with CIT, CUT, BAX, CCI and EIT. The final definition of the PCAs will be agreed upon in a partner workshop. Requirements for the PCAs will include: can be completed in four to eight weeks; cover INDUSAC cross-cutting areas; applicable to the wide range of sectors targeted; easily modifiable; future-oriented task definition; component of early phases of product development processes; enable further training of students and researchers; development of a deliverable for companies."

2. Introduction Predefined Collaborative Approaches

A Predefined Collaborative Approach can be described as a template for companies. This template provides a framework for companies to formulate their challenge and supports them in their formulation process. For this purpose, various fields are predefined in the templates. These fields must be filled in by the companies. In addition, information boxes provide examples of questions that companies can use as a guide. The fields and questions are designed to make companies think about important information, but also about boundary conditions that provide important information for solving the challenge. To provide more detail, each PCAs topic is explained in this report and the basic template in which all specific PCAs are designed is shown.

In total, there are nine different standardised (specific) templates (one per PCA) so that they can be filled with any content. Each template is based on the basic template but the templates differ in the results obtained, and in the tools and methods used. Each template has a title and a short explanation of the title which gives the area of the challenge. In this area, the challenge can be based on any company's needs. In consequence, the template can be used by any company in any sector (e.g. automotive, health, energy or any other).

This process allows that within one PCA there can be many different challenges. Thereby, any challenge can be published on INDUSAC using the presented PCAs.

The initial creation of ideas for PCAs was made by the authors of this deliverable based on their experience with research in live-labs at the IPEK – Institute of Product Engineering at KIT. The idea was to define the PCAs by defining the type of expected results (e.g., customer-specific future robust product properties, physical prototype, service platform mock-up, marketing campaign, etc.). With this method, companies later on using the PCAs would understand the expected output before writing the challenge and could therefore better adapt their input information to what the students need to know to reach the goal.

For creating the PCAs a workshop with specialists for method design and management in engineering was hosted at KIT. Together with the authors of this deliverable, nine specialists were part of the second step in the creation of the PCAs. All of the participants in the

workshop have experience with co-creation projects themselves. The session started with an introduction to INDUSAC and the goal behind the concept of PCAs. Then an online whiteboard with separate spaces was used to show existing ideas and to collect additional ideas for PCAs. The final step of this workshop included the detailing of the ideas and assigning methodical assistance to each idea.

Additional input was gathered through a collaborative workshop involving partners from both academia and industry in the third step. Four INDUSAC consortium partners, representing different countries, invited co-creation specialists to contribute to the refinement of the PCAs. Since PCAs are intentionally designed to accommodate challenges across diverse domains, such as automotive, medical, consumer electronics, and digital service platforms, having experts from different sectors participate was key. Each PCA-template features predefined fields, suggests guiding questions, and supplementary information, all aimed at assisting companies in framing their specific challenges. These fields and questions prompt companies to consider essential details and boundary conditions, which are crucial for the co-creation teams tasked with solving these challenges. However, it's important to note that the information gathered and provided through the PCAs should not replace direct communication between companies and student/researcher teams during the project. This information was emphasized in the workshop. The second step of this workshop included voting on the most relevant challenges and led to a reduction from a diversity of ideas in different levels of detail to the 9 PCAs as presented in the following.

The applicability of PCAs to various sectors underwent validation through feedback loops involving all consortium partners. The final PCAs, presented in both written and graphical formats, underwent additional reviews by all partners and further refinement by work package leaders. Throughout the project, the PCAs will continue to undergo iterative reviews and improvements.

II. PREDEFINED COLLABORATIVE APPROACHES

This section provides an overview of the topics of all nine PCAs. Each PCA is described in detail followed by the basic template that build the foundation for all nine specific templates (one per PCA). In the basic template the mandatory fields are marked with an asterisk and will be publicly visible.

The PCAs are in use on the INDUSAC platform and can all be seen in full detail when posting a challenge on the INDUSAC platform.

The PCAs help companies write challenges on the following topics:

- PCA1: Customer needs (and product properties) of tomorrow
- PCA2: Finding white spots in the product portfolio
- PCA3: Marketing campaign of the future
- PCA4: Feel the future platform - developing a digital platform based on a market analysis
- PCA5: Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Persona)
- PCA6: Service and product ideas of the future (Basis Scenarios)
- PCA7: Business plan – reduce your risk and optimise your planning
- PCA8: Innovative product ideas that solve the customer pain
- PCA9: Business model: Adding a service to my product – Building a PSS (product service system)

The following subsections describe the topics of the nine PCAs one by one followed by the basic template. The PCA are described in a style addressing the companies as they are the users of the PCA templates.

1. PCA1: Customer Needs (and Product Properties) of Tomorrow

Development of future-robust product properties based on scenarios and trend analysis.

In this challenge, the teams will derive future-robust product properties based on scenarios or a trend analysis. The future robustness results from the combined consideration of the weighted relevance of a product characteristic and its standard deviation. A high degree of future robustness indicates that the technical realisation of a product feature will make a major contribution to customer satisfaction even if various developments occur in the environment. A trend analysis makes it possible to analyse and depict social developments and their possible effects on companies. A trend as a (probable) future development first creates a feeling of being at the mercy of our environment and shows us that we cannot act independently of our environment. This unpleasant feeling is mitigated by counteracting the uncertainty about the future. The presentation of observable trends and their evaluation in

terms of probability of occurrence and impact on an element under consideration help in this. If you have already identified scenarios, you can provide them to the teams. If that is not the case their challenge will be based on a trend analysis. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). At the KO, you will get to know each other and have the chance to set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. In the next phase, the team will analyse the current product features in the product portfolio and present them in a first milestone meeting (MS1). The team then will focus on analysing the future. If scenarios are given to the team, they will base their research on these. Otherwise, their analysis will be based on trends that the teams will identify through their research. This is followed by a second milestone meeting (MS2), where you give feedback to the team on their findings. In the final phase, the teams derive future-robust product properties and prioritise them based on a cost-benefit analysis. A product property is considered future-robust if it appears in multiple scenarios or trends. This is followed by a final meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before the final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams (Figure 1). The time frame is between four to eight weeks. The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They will be able to choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed, to ensure the solution is developed in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click [here](#) (Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students (specific for each PCA)).

Figure 1 : Process timeline PCA1

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Scenario/trend analysis and references (e.g. Word)
- Catalogue of future robust product properties (e.g. Excel)

When using PCA1 the company is also asked to provide the team with existing scenarios or trends, if they have already worked with these methods and have it as input available. Then the students can start based on these starting points.

2. PCA2: Finding White Spots in the Product Portfolio

Development of an action plan to improve and/or develop relevant clusters within the product portfolio's elements based on a strategic analysis of the product portfolio.

In this challenge, the teams will develop an action plan on how to close white spots in your product portfolio based on a strategic analysis of your product portfolio. White spots are for example gaps or opportunities in a market that are currently underserved or not addressed by existing products or services in a company's product portfolio. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, the team will analyse your product portfolio in terms of product families or business units. The portfolio analysis the students carry out can be conducted based on existing or potential products, projects, resources, and knowledge within the portfolio. They are evaluated regarding the market attractiveness and competitive position. From this, statements are derived on how intensively investments in the marketing of individual products or product groups should be made. The result of the portfolio analysis is a simple graphic representation (portfolio display) of the complex relationships. The best-known portfolio representations are: Boston Consulting Group Portfolio (BSG-Portfolio, Four-field matrix) and McKinsey Portfolio (Nine-field-Matrix). The student teams might use these types, but have the freedom to select a different portfolio representation if more suited. Having positioned the products in terms of their importance in the market, they will target the clusters that need improvement. They will present the identified product clusters in a first milestone meeting (MS1). The teams will then focus on the white spots and refine them to derive an action plan. This is followed by a final meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks (Figure 2). The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each PCA\)](#)).

Figure 2 : Process timeline of PCA2

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Strategic analysis of product portfolio (e.g. BCG-matrix)
- Clustering of product portfolio (e.g. PowerPoint)
- Action-plan/white spot analysis for relevant clusters

When using PCA2 the company is also asked to share a presentation of the product portfolio and future product ideas if that can be made available to the teams. Both can be used as basis to start solving the challenge.

3. PCA3: Marketing Campaign of the Future

Design a marketing campaign based on a market analysis with a focus on customers and trend analysis.

In this challenge, the teams will create a marketing campaign that targets your future customers. They will base their assumptions on market, customer, and trend analysis. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, they will analyse and understand today's customers and then look at future customers. They will also analyse your current marketing strategy to get a deeper understanding of it as a basis for future campaigns. They will present their findings up to this point in the first milestone (MS1). Based on their findings and your feedback, they will focus on future trends and start creating the marketing campaign. With a trend analysis, changes in social values and currents of different social classes can be determined and their effect on companies. On this basis, statements about future developments can be made and suitable proposals for product policy and marketing strategies can be developed. This will be based on future customers and trends and will be in line with your corporate marketing strategy. This is followed by a final meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks (Figure 3). The suggested methods and templates will also be provided to the teams. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution is developed in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each PCA\)](#)).

Figure 3 : Process timeline PCA3

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Market analysis with a focus on customers
- Trend analysis combining future customers and marketing trends
- Design of a marketing campaign

When using PCA3 the company is advised to provide reference of marketing campaigns that were a huge success or that failed. Furthermore, they can provide insights on upcoming trends they see.

4. PCA4: Feel the Future Platform – Developing a Digital Platform Based on a Market Analysis

Development of a digital platform prototype based on a market analysis.

In this challenge, the team will build a prototype of a new platform for your company based on a market analysis. In the market analysis the teams study the attractiveness and the dynamics of a market within your industry. They focus on changes in customer needs and customer behaviour. They will also consider competitors, their goals and their strategies which play a central role. A market analysis is part of the industry analysis and thus in turn of the global environmental analysis but can also be conducted individually. It can be conducted for example through a SWOT analysis. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). At the KO, you will get to know each other and have the chance to set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, the teams will identify the products or services for which your company needs the platform and determine your requirements. In the first milestone meeting (MS1), the team will present their current findings and align with your company representative on the goal of the platform. The next step is to analyse the market in terms of competitors and your company's marketing and sales strategy. The team presents their findings in a second milestone meeting (MS2). In the final phase, they conceptualise the platform and build a virtual prototype. In this case, the goal is the development of a click dummy or mock-up of a digital platform. If you agree on a different kind of prototype with your teams, that is an option as well. This is followed by a final meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks (Figure 4). The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They will be able to choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed, to ensure the solution is developed in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here (Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students (specific for each PCA)).

Figure 4 : Process timeline PCA4

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Market analysis to define the platform
- Digital Platform prototype (click dummy) (based on existing product profiles)

When using PCA4 the company can give platforms, websites or other sales channels they consider relevant as references. If prior market research results are available, it is recommended to provide them to the students. Companies should make sure that if they want a specific tool to be used or an existing platform to be build on they should provide it to the teams.

5. PCA5: Service and Product Ideas of the Future (Basis Persona)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple personas, and appropriate product properties.

In this challenge, the students will derive new service or product ideas for your company based on an analysis of your relevant target group. A product idea is a possibility of how to realize the characteristics of the product defined in a product profile. Part of a product idea is the product claim, product description, picture, functional structure, system structure, validation, and satisfaction of customer and user, as well as strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the idea. The students solving this challenge will get templates to specify product ideas and product profiles. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, they will analyse your target group and create Personas to better understand your customers. Personas are fictive persons who are typical representatives of a target group. The students solving this challenge will get templates to create personas. In a first milestone meeting (MS1), they will present the

Personas to your company representative to ensure that they have correctly understood the company's customer profiles. Based on the Personas, they will derive several product ideas. The team will work out a maximum of three detailed service or product ideas. In the second milestone meeting (MS2), they will present these services or ideas and you will decide together which of these ideas they should analyse further with a value proposition analysis. The value proposition will be the core of the next and last phase. In the final meeting (FM) the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before the final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks (Figure 5). The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each PCA\)](#))).

Figure 5 : Process timeline PCA5

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Persona
- Product Profile
- Service/ Product idea

When using PCA5 companies that want students to focus on specific already identified target groups should provide them to the teams.

6. PCA6: Service and Product Ideas of the Future (Basis Scenarios)

Development of a service or product idea based on one or multiple trends/scenarios, and appropriate future-robust product properties.

In this challenge, the students will derive new service or product ideas for your company based on scenarios or a trend analysis. Scenarios describe possible manifestations of the future based on various development possibilities of several networked key factors. If you have already identified scenarios, you can provide them to the student teams. If that is not the case their challenge will be based on a trend analysis. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. The teams then focus on analysing the future. If the students are given scenarios, they will base their research on these. Otherwise, their analysis will be based on trends that the teams have identified through their research. The future robustness of the student's research results from the combined consideration of the weighted relevance of a product characteristic and its standard deviation. A high degree of future robustness indicates that the technical realisation of a product feature will make a major contribution to customer satisfaction even if various developments occur in the environment. Therefore, the student teams will focus on deriving properties that are future robust. This is followed by a first milestone meeting (MS1) where you give feedback to the team on their findings. Based on the trends or scenarios, they will derive several product ideas and work out the best ones. In the second milestone meeting (MS2), they will present these services or ideas to you, and you will decide together which of these ideas they should analyse further with a value proposition analysis. The value proposition will be the next and last phase. In the final meeting (FM) the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks (Figure 6). The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each PCA\)](#)).

Figure 6 : Process timeline PCA6

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Persona
- Product Profile
- Service/ Product idea

When using PCA6 companies can either provide teams with already identified scenarios if they have them, or let them start from scratch. Both options are possible.

7. PCA7: Business Plan – Reduce Your Risk and Optimise Your Planning

The development of a business plan after a SWOT analysis and an estimation of profitability.

In this challenge, the students will develop a business plan after a SWOT analysis and will then estimate the profitability of the business plan they've developed. SWOT analysis (or SWOT matrix) is a strategic planning and strategic management technique used to help a person or organization identify Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats related to business competition or project planning. To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, they will conduct a SWOT analysis of your business in total and determine how each finding impacts the business and its goals. They determine if a finding is positive or negative and identify any areas of concern that may need to be addressed in the business plan. In a first milestone meeting (MS1), the team presents the findings to your company representative to make sure early in the process, that they understood the goals of the company. Within this milestone, you can see how the analysis develops and guide the team in the right direction. Based on their results, they will prepare a business model canvas and write a business plan that fixes the weaknesses and threats identified in the SWOT analysis and pushes the opportunities and strengths to the next level. They will present the business plan in the second milestone meeting (MS2) and discuss it with your company representative. Based on the feedback from the milestone meeting and their findings, they will evaluate the business plan with an estimation of the profitability of the business. This is followed by a final milestone meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks (Figure 7). The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the

information provided, please click [here](#) (Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students (specific for each PCA)).

Figure 7 : Process timeline PCA7

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- SWOT-Analysis
- Business plan
- Estimation of profitability

When using PCA7 companies can provide the teams with former business plans if they want them to have them as references. Furthermore, if they want the teams to use specific tools for the estimation of profitability they should state so.

8. PCA8: Innovative Product Ideas That Solve the Customer Pain

Based on a specified customer need, new product ideas should be developed and shown in a virtual prototype.

In this challenge, the students will develop alternative product ideas based on specific customer needs that you provide the teams with. After a detailed analysis, they will build a prototype based on a product idea. The prototype visualizes the mental ideas and supports the understanding of complexity. It is built to validate the potential solutions. Furthermore, prototypes enable communication and thus help overcome for example cultural and language barriers. They also test functionalities and requirements. In this case, the prototype is built as a virtual prototype with the help of for example specific software (tools). To make the challenge a success, the following process is recommended for your cooperation with the team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. In the next phase, they derive product ideas based on the given customer pain points and existing product profiles (your description and details on the customer needs that you identified before the challenge). To evaluate their ideas, they will perform a utility analysis. In the first milestone meeting (MS1), they will present their current findings. Your company representative and the team will assess which product idea should be built as a virtual prototype. The students will build the virtual prototype in the next phase. This is followed by a final milestone meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks (Figure 8). The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here (Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students (specific for each PCA)).

Figure 8 : Process timeline PCA8

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Development of alternative product ideas
- Utility analysis and evaluation of ideas
- Virtual prototype

When using PCA8 already identified customer needs need to be given to the teams. This challenge works with this specific input from the company.

9. PCA9: Business Model: Adding a Service to my Product – Building a PSS (Product Service System)

The development of new business models for a given product.

In this challenge, students develop new business models for a given product. This is based on a target group analysis using the persona method. A Product Service System (PSS) is a market proposition that extends the traditional functionality of a product by incorporating additional services. To make the challenge a success, we recommend the following process for your cooperation with the student team: You will meet the team at an initial online kick-off meeting (KO). There you will get to know each other and set expectations. The team will then work independently on the challenge in several phases. Firstly, the team will familiarise themselves with the details and methods of the challenge and investigate your company in more detail. Next, they will analyse your target group and create Personas to better understand your customers. In a first milestone meeting (MS1), they will present the Personas to your company representative to ensure that they have correctly understood the company's customer profiles. Based on the Personas, they will derive three alternative business models including utility analyses. The utility analysis is a powerful planning method and is here used to systematically prepare decisions by evaluating (determining benefits) and selecting (ranking based on benefits) optimal alternatives (evaluation objects). It is particularly

suitable for cases in which the total benefit is composed of a wide variety of partial benefits and the monetary profit is insufficient as the sole criterion for decision-making. The utility analysis allows for the collection of both objective and subjective information. This is followed by a final milestone meeting (FM) where the team presents their final solution and receives feedback from you. They will incorporate the final feedback into their deliverables before final submission.

The timeline presented here is a suggestive guide for the teams. The time frame is between four to eight weeks (Figure 9). The teams will also be provided with the suggested methods and templates. They can choose whether or not to use them, but it is highly recommended to do so. Furthermore, it is recommended to do the milestones proposed to ensure that the solution develops in the desired direction. If you would like to know more about the information provided, please click here ([Link to the area, where Innoget provides the download area for students \(specific for each PCA\)](#)).

Figure 9 : Process timeline PCA9

When solving the challenge, it is expected to deliver the following outputs:

- Persona (user behaviour)
- Business model
- 3 alternatives and subsequent utility analysis

10. PCA Basic Template

The PCAs all follow a specific scheme to make posting challenges as easy and intuitive as possible. The following section shows the basic template which was used to create each specific PCA template. To design a specific template out of the basic template, different prefilled text was added to the text boxes to explain to the readers (companies) how they should fill the boxes for each PCA. In the following the prefilled text that is the same for each PCA is shown, and the PCA-specific text is removed (for example each challenge, no matter with which specific PCA template it is built, needs a short description given by the company). The specific PCAs include additional information boxes to give hints on how to fill a specific field. These are not included here, since they are PCA-specific but they are marked with a circled “i” to give a feeling for the place where help could be needed when filling out the PCA-template. The template finishes with the INDUSAC submission agreement, which needs to be accepted before a challenge can be submitted. The submission agreement is followed by the final question concerning privacy settings. Here the option is between posting the

challenge as a sub-user from the company or with the company profile. Especially for companies that have multiple challenges from different departments, having a company representative assigned to the challenge can help. If this information should not be visible, the challenge can be posted from the company profile without a sub-user visible.

The final specific PCA templates are already implemented on the INDUSAC platform (<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/>).

*Enter a Title for your Challenge: 4 - 15 words

Title

*Upload a picture to represent your Challenge:

Picture

*Short description: 50 - 100 words

Describe your challenge briefly.

*Initial Problem description: 50 - 250 words

What is the concrete problem you want to address with this challenge? Which problems should the teams solve for you? Be as precise as possible.
Do not disclose any classified technical or business information since challenges will be visible on a public website.

*Context: 50 - 200 words

Use Cases – in which context does this problem/ challenge appear?
What is the context of the problem to be solved? Give a broad overview of the problem

*Connection to Cross-cutting areas: 20 - 50 words

How is your challenge connected to one of the areas: Circularity, General Sustainability, Industry 4.0, and Digitalisation

Categorization:

Giving a good categorization is the key to your challenge to be found by appropriate teams (Figure 10).

Type in a search term

Aerospace + Agriculture and Marine Resources + Agrofood Industry + Biological Sciences + Communications + Computer related +

Consumer related + Digitalization + Electronics Related Market + Electronics, IT and Telecomms + Energy Market +

Energy Technology + Genetic Engineering / Molecular Biology + Industrial Products + Industrial Technologies +

Industrial manufacturing, Material and Transport Technologies + Lightweight + Measurements and Standards + Medical Health related +

Ophthalmology + Other + Physical Sciences and Exact Sciences + Protecting Man and Environment + Social and Economics concerns +

Sustainability +

Figure 10 : Categorization PCA

*Input: 5 - 50 words

****PCA specific****

*Expectations: 10 - 100 words

****PCA specific****

Desired team profile: 10 - 20 words

Would you like to have any specific skills or academia background in the team that is solving your challenge?

Additional Information: 10 - 200 words

****PCA specific****

Indicate the maximum number of teams you can work with:

To ensure a good quality of collaboration, set a maximum number of teams you can work with to provide sufficient resources, especially your time, to work with the teams.

Select challenge manager

Only select this option if you want some of your sub-users to manage this challenge publication and all upcoming submissions from platform members.

 Click to select challenge manager among your company account sub-users

*INDUSAC submission agreement

The teams interested in submitting a proposal for your challenge will carefully read the terms of the INDUSAC agreement and submit the proposal if they agree and accept the INDUSAC

terms set out in the agreement. Additional agreements between students, researchers and companies can be set to specify the cooperation. Additional agreements are subordinates of the INDUSAC submission agreement, and thus INDUSAC is not liable for any subordinate agreements or contracts. If there is a conflict, the INDUSAC submission agreement prevails.

View the Submission Agreement provided by INDUSAC

- I agree to use this submission agreement*
- Create an additional submission agreement

* Privacy settings for this Challenge

- Post as [Name sub-user] from Company
- Post as Company

III. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the PCAs are an excellent tool for creating challenges as they provide a structured framework that can be easily adapted by companies to suit their different situations and contexts. By using the PCAs, companies can save time and effort while ensuring that their challenges are consistent, well organised and engaging for teams. In addition, the PCAs help companies to identify and clarify the objectives of their challenges. Overall, the PCAs are a valuable resource for creating challenges that are challenging, fun, effective and motivating for collaborative teams.

The PCAs provide a structure that allows companies to clearly define the challenge, explain the goals and purpose of the challenge, and set the criteria for desired solutions.

IV. LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 : Process timeline PCA1	10
Figure 2 : Process timeline of PCA2	11
Figure 3 : Process timeline PCA3	13
Figure 4 : Process timeline PCA4	14
Figure 5 : Process timeline PCA5	15
Figure 6 : Process timeline PCA6	49
Figure 7 : Process timeline PCA7	51
Figure 8 : Process timeline PCA8	52
Figure 9 : Process timeline PCA9	53
Figure 10 : Categorization PCA.....	55

